

Simultaneous Diffusion and Chemical Reaction in a Semi-infinite-finite Medium

PRADIP KUMAR SEN

Mahadevananda Mahavidyalaya, Barrackpur, West Bengal

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A problem of simultaneous diffusion and chemical reaction in a semi-infinite-finite medium has been worked out by powerful operational method due to Heaviside¹. Expressions for concentration distribution in a finite and infinite medium are obtained. Some important conclusions are drawn from the different theoretical graphs.

THE process of simultaneous diffusion and chemical reaction is very important in connection with the reactions in high polymer substances². In addition to this, diffusion may take place within the pores of a solid which can absorb some of the diffusing substances. Examples involving diffusion into living cells and micro-organisms can be cited from biology and biochemistry.

There had been a considerable amount of studies³⁻⁶ on simultaneous diffusion and chemical reaction, but the corresponding problem for any composite medium has not been discussed so far to the best of the knowledge of this author. Hence in this paper, the author has discussed one of the problems of composite medium, viz. of a semi-infinite-finite one.

Explanation of the symbols used :

C_1, D_1 and K_1 are the concentration, diffusion coefficient and first-order-reaction-constant respectively, in the first region $-1 < x < 0$ and $C_2, D_2,$ and K_2 are the corresponding quantities in the second region $x > 0$.

x =Variable length measured along the direction of flow of diffusing substance.

l =Length of the finite region.

C_0 =Constant concentration of the surface at $x = -1$.

t =Variable time.

$D = \frac{d}{dt}$ (Operator).

Fundamental equations, boundary conditions and solution of the problem.

If the diffusing substance is immobilized by an irreversible first order reaction so that the rate of removal of diffusing substance for the first medium is $K_1 C_1$, then for the first medium the well known Fick's law of diffusion in one dimension reduces to

$$D_1 \frac{\partial^2 C_1}{\partial x^2} - K_1 C_1 = \frac{\partial C_1}{\partial t}, \quad -1 < x < 0, t > 0. \quad \dots (1)$$

Similarly for the second medium the equation for diffusion in presence of chemical reaction is

$$D_2 \frac{\partial^2 C_2}{\partial x^2} - K_2 C_2 = \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial t}, \quad x > 0, t > 0. \quad \dots (2)$$

Let the source (at constant concentration C_0) is placed in the first medium at $x = -1$ and the sink (at zero concentration) is situated at a large distance in the second medium, i. e.

$$C_1 = C_0, \quad x = -1, t > 0, \quad \dots (3)$$

$$C_2 \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty, t > 0. \quad \dots (4)$$

Assuming that at the surface of separation $x=0$ there is no interface resistance and no accumulation of diffusing substance, we have

$$C_1 = C_2, \quad x = 0, t > 0, \quad \dots (5)$$

$$D_1 \left(\frac{\partial C_1}{\partial x} \right) = D_2 \left(\frac{\partial C_2}{\partial x} \right), \quad x = 0, t > 0. \quad \dots (6)$$

With initial concentrations of the two media zero (i. e. there is no flow at $t=0$), equations (1) & (2) in operational form become

$$\frac{\partial^2 C_1}{\partial x^2} - \left(\frac{D+K_1}{D_1} \right) C_1 = 0, \quad -1 < x < 0, \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 C_2}{\partial x^2} - \left(\frac{D+K_2}{D_2} \right) C_2 = 0, \quad x > 0 \quad \dots (8)$$

Writing $(D+K_1)/D_1 = q_1^2$ and $(D+K_2)/D_2 = q_2^2$ the equations (7) and (8) become

$$\frac{\partial^2 C_1}{\partial x^2} - q_1^2 C_1 = 0, \quad -1 < x < 0, \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 C_2}{\partial x^2} - q_2^2 C_2 = 0, \quad x > 0, \quad \dots (10)$$

The solutions of equations (9) and (10) are

$$C_1 = A_1 \cosh q_1 x + B_1 \sinh q_1 x, \quad \dots (11)$$

$$C_2 = A_2 \cosh q_2 x + B_2 \sinh q_2 x, \quad \dots (12)$$

where A_1, B_1, A_2 and B_2 are arbitrary constants to be determined from the boundary conditions.

Evaluating the arbitrary constants from equations(3), (4), (5) and (6), the equations (11) and (12) turn out to be

$$C_1 = C_0 \frac{\cosh q_1 x - \sigma' \sinh q_1 x}{\cosh q_1 l + \sigma' \sinh q_1 l}, \quad (13)$$

$$C_2 = C_0 \frac{\exp(-q_2 x)}{\cosh q_1 l + \sigma' \sinh q_1 l}, \quad \dots (14)$$

where $\sigma' = (D_2 K_2)/(D_1 K_1)^{1/2}$.

Expanding the hyperbolic sines and cosines and simplifying,

$$C_1 = C_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[m^n \exp \left(-q_1 \left\{ (2n+1)l+x \right\} \right) - m^{n+1} \exp \left(-q_1 \left\{ (2n+1)l-x \right\} \right) \right] \dots (15)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{2C_0}{1+\sigma'} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} m^n \exp \left[- \left\{ q_2 x + q_1 (2n+1)l \right\} \right].$$

where $m = (\sigma' - 1)/(\sigma' + 1)$ (16)

Assuming that K_1 and K_2 are small and expanding their exponential functions and retaining the same only upto the first power of K_1 and K_2 , the operational solutions of equations (15) and (16) are given by

$$C_1 = C_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \alpha^n \left[\operatorname{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+x}{2(D_1 t)^{1/2}} - \alpha \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l-x}{2(D_1 t)^{1/2}} - \frac{K_1 t}{(D_1 t)^{3/2}} \left\{ \left((2n+1)l+x \right) i \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+x}{2(D_1 t)^{1/2}} - \alpha \left((2n+1)l-x \right) i \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l-x}{2(D_1 t)^{1/2}} \right\} + 4Kt \left\{ (n+1)\alpha i^2 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l-x}{2(D_1 t)^{1/2}} - n i^2 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+x}{2(D_1 t)^{1/2}} \right\} \right], \dots (17)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{2\sigma' C_0}{(1+\sigma')} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \alpha^n \left[\operatorname{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+\sigma x}{2(D_1 t)^{1/2}} - \left\{ \frac{K_1 (2n+1)l}{D_1^{1/2}} + \frac{K_2 x}{D_2^{1/2}} \right\} i^{1/2} \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+\sigma x}{2(D_1 t)^{1/2}} + \frac{2Kt}{\sigma'} \left\{ i - (2n+1)\sigma \right\} i^2 \operatorname{erfc} \frac{(2n+1)l+\sigma x}{2(D_1 t)^{1/2}} \right], \dots (18)$$

where $\sigma = (D_1/D_2)^{1/2}$, $\alpha = (1-\sigma)/(1+\sigma)$ and $K = \sigma(K_1 - K_2)/(1-\sigma^2)$

Equations (17) and (18) are in agreement with those obtained by Crank³ in absence of chemical reaction (i.e. when $K_1 = 0$ and $K_2 = 0$).

Equations (17) and (18) are computed by using $D_2 = 100 D_1$ and $(D_1 t/l^2)^{1/2} = 0.5$.

Four graphs are drawn : (i) distance vs. concentration in the first medium (with $K_1 t = 1.5$ and $K_2 t = 0.5$) in figure 1, (ii) distance vs. concentration in the second medium (with $K_1 t = 1.5$ and $K_2 t = 0.5$) in figure 2, (iii) $K_1 t$ vs. concentration in the first medium (with $K_2 t = 0.5$) in figure 3 and (iv) $K_2 t$ vs. concentration in the second medium (with $K_1 t = 1.5$) in figure 4.

Discussion

From Figure 1 it is clear that the deviation of the full curve from the dashed curve is very small for points near the surface of separation. Gradually this deviation increases as x decreases, becoming maximum when x is about $-l/2$; after that the deviation decreases as x decreases becoming nil when x is equal to $-l$. That is, the effect of chemical reaction on the concentration is maximum for points lying about the mid-point of the first medium and the effect gradually decreases as the distance from that point increases.

Fig. 1. Concentration distribution curves for the first medium are drawn for two conditions : (i) in presence of chemical reaction (represented by a full curve) and (ii) in absence of chemical reaction (represented by a dashed curve).

Fig. 2. Concentration distribution curves for the second medium are drawn for two conditions : (i) in presence of chemical reaction (represented by a full curve) and (ii) in absence of chemical reaction (represented by a dashed curve).

From Figure 2 it is obvious that in the second medium the effect of chemical reaction on the concentration is maximum for points near the surface of separation, which decreases as x increases and tends to zero for large values of x .

Fig 3 indicates that at a particular time the concentration at a point in the first medium decreases as K_1 increases and similarly in the second medium the concentration at a point decreases as K_2 increases (vide Fig 4). For both media the rate of decrease of concentration being somewhat more rapid for a large value of the distance from the surface of separation than for a small value of the same.

Fig. 3. Variation of concentration in the first medium as a function of constant of first order reaction K_1 , for different values of x .

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Fig. 4. Variation of concentration in the second medium as a function of constant of first order reaction K_2 , for different values of x .

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